

Assessing the Integrity of Deep Foundations Using Thermal Integrity Profiling (TIP)

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ABSTRACT:

Thermal integrity profiling (TIP) is a non-destructive, innovative technique used to evaluate the structural integrity of concrete foundations. The heat released by early-age concrete as it cures causes variations in local temperature due to abnormalities in the concrete shaft. Temperature sensors installed on the reinforcement cage collect detailed temperature data across the full concrete pile in order to accurately identify these temperature changes during concrete curing. Using the heat produced during the concrete or grout curing process, this testing technique evaluates the integrity of the deep foundation over the measured length. The tests were conducted on two bored concrete 1200 mm diameter instrumented bidirectional static load test piles (namely, PTP1 and PTP2) in Dubai, United Arab Emirates. For both test piles, a temperature drop was observed at the sacrificial jack assembly position, which was brought about by heat loss as a result of the assembly behaving as a heat sink. Thermal data show that the effective average radius is usually in line with the intended 1200 mm diameter up to the depths of around 22.0 m for PTP1 and 39.0 m for PTP2. The radius decreases by more than 6% below this depth to the design toe level of the piles, suggesting a temperature reduction that may be caused by the presence of slightly lower quality concrete. The results show that TIP was able to provide reliable and comprehensive temperature data in a cost-effective way for assessing the pile integrity.

Keywords: deep foundations, thermal integrity, pile anomaly detection, heat transfer, concrete quality.

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INTRODUCTION

The integrity and quality of cast-in-situ foundation piles pose significant challenges for the construction engineering profession [1]. Sun et. al. [1] stated that "in recent years, shaft repair and the associated maintenance accounted for a significant part of the construction cost in different parts of the world. It is crucial to ensure the pile quality at the construction stage". However, the inherent characteristics of these deep structures, such as limited accessibility, poor visibility, and considerable depth, create significant obstacles for inspecting structural quality during construction [2,3]. The ability to control the temperature rise and fall in concrete at an early age is well recognized as one factor preserving the structure's long-term performance and durability. To minimize uncertainty regarding concrete quality or shaft geometry, pile integrity testing procedures have been developed. A viable alternative to the Cross-hole Sonic Logging (CSL) method is Thermal Integrity Profiling (TIP), which has only recently gained momentum in the construction industry. Within TIP, pile

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integrity is measured indirectly by the hydration heat generated during concrete hardening. The thermal integrity test has proven to be an effective method to evaluate the integrity of newly constructed drilled shafts to identify anomalies in deep concrete foundations [4]. In addition, as an off-centre cage would show higher and lower temperatures on opposite sides of the shaft, the approach can also be used to evaluate the alignment of the reinforcement cage within the shaft [1,5]. TIP uses the heat generated by curing concrete in a process called hydration to assess the quality of cast-in-place concrete foundations such as bored trial and production piles [6], continuous flight auger piles, drilled displacement piles, rectangular barrettes, etc. However, due to time and economic constraints of the fast-track projects, TIP was used in selected prestigious projects in the region.

THERMAL INTEGRITY PROFILING (TIP)

The Thermal Integrity Profiling (TIP) was originally described in the USA in 2007 [7]. The American standard for testing materials [8] on TIP for concrete deep foundations was released and contains general specifications for measurement equipment. The German Geotechnical Society's Piling Committee released guidelines for the first time in 2019 covering the use of TIP for integrity testing of bored piles in Germany [9,10]. This paper examines the field case study of the performance of thermal integrity testing of two concrete bored bidirectional static load test piles. A general TIP temperature evaluation criterion for the quality of a pile is given below (Table 1).

Table 1. General TIP Evaluation Criteria

Evaluation class	Temperature deviation of thermal anomaly compared to reference value	Geometrical extent of thermal anomaly
A1	$\Delta T \leq 6\%$	Not applicable
A2	Reduced temperature in the range $\Delta T > 6\%$ of reference value. Up to 10% acceptable in soil and soft rocks prone to collapse.	Locally occurred and insignificant, for example 2 out of 4 sensors in the cross section.
A3	$\Delta T > 10\%$	Significant, occurrence in several sensors in the cross section.
B	$\Delta T > 12\%$	>30cm of the pile length

Many of the limitations of the Cross-hole Sonic Logging (CSL) and Low Strain approaches can be addressed by the Thermal Integrity Profiling (TIP) technique. Compared to other traditional integrity testing techniques, this method provides many benefits. The main ones are listed in the Use of Thermal Integrity Profiling (TIP) in Drilled Shaft Evaluation [11]:

- TIP procedures using the thermal wires are simpler to install and enable automated data collection.
- TIP can identify integrity defects outside the reinforcing cage and is significant for side resistance, structural integrity, and durability of shafts.
- TIP data can be used to identify misalignment of the reinforcing cage.
- It is possible to identify soft pile-toe conditions, particularly when time records are taken into account.
- TIP is performed using thermal sacrificial wires, with data collection beginning just before the time of concrete placement and continuing until at least 12 hours after the peak temperature has been observed.
- The continuous record of concrete temperatures facilitates the most effective detection of concrete defects because the maximum temperature deviation can be computed by evaluating results throughout the test period.
- For deep and large-diameter shafts that are subject to mass concrete considerations, temperature data can be of additional value.

SUBSURFACE GEOLOGY

The general geological conditions in Dubai essentially consist, of a linear coastline dissected by creeks [12]. Superficial deposits consisting of beach dune sands with marine sands and silts [12]. Furthermore, erosion, capillary rise phenomena, and evaporation have led to extensive silt deposits in some areas, especially near the creeks [12]. These superficial deposits are underlined by alternating layers of calcarenite, carbonate sandstone, siltstone, and conglomerate, as well as cemented sand layers [12,13]. The general site stratigraphy is given in Table 2 (m DMD - Meter Dubai Municipality Datum).

Table 2. General Stratigraphy of the Study Area

Elevation (mDMD)	Description of Strata
0.00 to -8.00	Slightly silty gravelly sand
-8.00 to -11.00	Alternate layers of sand and Calcarenite
-11.00 to -22.00	Very weak, Calcarenite/Sandstone interbedded with sand
-22.00 to -67.00	Very weak, fine-grained Calcisiltite/Siltstone interbedded with Conglomerate and Sandstone
-67.00 to -86.00	Very weak, fine-grained Siltstone interbedded with Sandstone and Conglomerate

TEST METHODOLOGY

Thermal Integrity Profiling (TIP) testing was performed using Thermal Wire cable and Thermal Acquisition Ports (TAPs) [14]. The TIP system, manufactured by Pile Dynamics, USA, measures concrete temperatures during curing using cables embedded in the concrete [14]. TIP tests are typically performed within 48 hours following the casting of concrete piles up to 1000 mm in diameter; however, larger piles may require an additional few hours of data collection to obtain the complete temperature profile. There are two preliminary instrumented test piles, namely, PTP1 and PTP2, which were used for TIP testing (Table 3). The PTP1 was over-drilled by around 8.40m below the design toe level. The cable was installed up to the design toe level, and hence the analysis was carried out for that length only.

Table 3. Details of Test Piles

Pile ID	Pile Diameter (mm)	Pile top level (m)	Pile design toe level (m)	BDSL Jack level (m)
PTP1	1200	0.00	-23.00	-13.70
PTP2	1200	0.00	-41.00	-26.50

Thermal wire cables consist of temperature sensors spaced every 12 inches along the length of a cable. For these piles, four cables were attached along the full length of the rebar cage, ensuring each wire was placed with minimum likelihood of being damaged either during lifting and placement operations or by the tremie pipe insertion during the concreting process [14]. To ensure continuity and high confidence in getting data successfully, each wire was individually checked prior to installation to indicate full working condition [14]. After the concrete placement was complete, one Thermal Aggregator (TAG) and three TAP-Edge data loggers were attached to the thermal wires. Once the data loggers were connected, data acquisition began. During concrete curing, the hydrating cement generates heat, which increases the temperature of the pile concrete. Every 15-minute duration, the TAG and TAP-Edge data loggers record the measured temperature at each sensor location along the length of the wire, generating a profile of temperature versus depth at each increment of time [14]. The TAG device transmits data via a cloud-based cellular connection and monitors the data during the curing process. After it was evident that the concrete had reached peak temperature, the data was downloaded from the cloud for further processing and analysis.

By computing a temperature-to-radius (T-R) factor based on the average radius (R_{avg}) and average temperature (T_{avg}), the thermal profile is converted into an effective radius profile [14]. The reported volume placed over the shaft length is used for determining the average radius [14].

$$R_{avg} = \sqrt{V/(\pi L)} \quad (1)$$

Where V = concrete volume placed, and L = concreted shaft length [14]

In their study, Pisciacko and Ellisi [14] note that “the average temperature is based on the measured overall average temperature at the time increment selected for analysis. The local temperatures (i.e., measured at each node and along each thermal cable) are then multiplied by the T-R factor to yield the effective radius profile. The term "effective radius" is generally defined as the radius of intact concrete that would produce the measured temperature” [15]. On the other hand, differences in concrete quality and geometry along the shaft length are included in the effective radius. Therefore, the effective radius profile is better recognized as an adjusted model of the shaft incorporating both the measured temperature profile and shaft installation records. When considering the effective radii as a geometric parameter, local concrete cover at a specific location can be estimated by subtracting the nominal cage radius from the TIP-computed effective local radii [14].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TIP results for the tested shafts include the measured temperature and calculated effective radius versus depth. The effective radius calculations were based on the measured thermal profile and the recorded concrete volume in Table 4.

Table 4. Concrete Consumption Details

Pile ID	Pile Diameter (mm)	Theoretical concrete volume (m ³)	Actual concrete volume (m ³)	Variation (%)
PTP1	1200	26.00	26.30	1.14
PTP2	1200	46.40	47.20	1.69

The thermal profiles present the measured temperature versus depth for each active sensor at the selected time interval [14]. The optimal time selected for analysis of the shaft profile usually corresponds to the time when maximum or peak temperature occurs [14]. The time to peak temperature and also the time selected for analysis for PTP1 was 22 hours and 16 minutes after connecting the data loggers. The time to peak temperature and also the time selected for analysis for PTP2 was 30 hours and 4 minutes after connecting the data loggers. In general, temperature variations are within the normal range for TIP results due to the accuracy of the temperature sensor [14]. Any anomalies would be signified by sudden drops in temperature at a specific depth [14]. The temperature versus depth results for PTP1 and PTP2 are illustrated in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2.

The concrete consumption (Table 3) for PTP1 was 26.30 m³ and that of PTP2 was 47.20 m³. This refers to a slight increase of 1.14% and 1.69% of the theoretical volume as anticipated. There is a reduction in temperature observed for PTP1 at 22.90 m and 40.50 m for PTP2; it indicates the presence of lower-quality concrete as well as a reduction in the grout cover (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2). Additionally, a predicted temperature drop at the jack assembly site (at depths of 13.70 m and 26.50 m) was attributed to heat loss, as the assembly functions as a heat sink. The analysis indicates that the effective average radius reduction of both piles surpasses the standard reference value of 6%. The graphs illustrating temperature deviation over time are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. The temperature decline at the top of the shafts is due to heat loss from the concrete-air interface, while at the toe, it results from heat loss at the concrete-soil interface.

At the start of measurements, the temperature slightly dropped along the four profiles, as shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. This phenomenon can be attributed to the initial temperature of the concrete being

higher than that of the ground. The initial curing process of the concrete was relatively slow, as it required time to achieve equilibrium before sufficient heat was generated from hydration to offset the heat lost to the cooler ground [17]. Subsequently, the piles started to warm up, with the exception of the upper few centimetres, where the concrete was exposed to the ambient air during the night [1].

Figure 1. Temperature Versus Depth Profile for PTP1

Figure 2. Temperature Versus Depth Profile for PTP2

Approximately at 22 hours and 30 hours, the temperature variation profiles of both piles attained their peak values. Following this, the temperature began to decline gradually at a very slow pace. The aforementioned temperature profiles are influenced by a combination of factors, including the

heat generated from hydration of the concrete and the rate of heat transfer between the pile and the surrounding soil [1]. Given that the measured temperature profile against depth for each individual thermal cable shows slight inconsistencies [1], the piles are regarded as non-uniform in shape, and it is presumed that some form of defect was present in the piles due to the jack assembly.

Figure 3. Temperature Deviation with Time Plot for PTP1

Figure 4. Temperature Deviation with Time Plot for PTP2

The change of thermal properties between different soil and rock strata affects the heat dissipation rate from the concrete body to the surrounding ground and leads to longitudinal temperature variation [16,17]. The occurrence of Siltstone, Sandstone, Calcisiltite, and similar materials in the study area, which possess relatively higher thermal conductivity, facilitates quicker heat transfer; consequently, lower temperatures are expected to be observed within the respective strata on the longitudinal temperature profile [1]. Additionally, factors such as porosity, mineral composition, and the presence of groundwater can significantly impact the thermal conductivity.

CONCLUSION

This paper discusses the benefits of TIP in detecting early-age concrete to assess the integrity of deep foundations and cost savings as compared to other traditional testing methods. The advantage of using thermal cables is their capacity to provide a high spatial density of temperature data as well as the ease of installation during construction [1]. This method allows for the assessment of the entire cross-section of the embedded foundation element, encompassing the regions outside the reinforcing cage and extending along the full length [14]. Integrity concerns within the shaft can lead to considerable financial repercussions and delays in the construction schedule, as the assessment of the pile's static capacity, serviceability, and structural safety relies on the awareness of any existing anomalies [18] within the piles. This innovative integrity testing method offers valuable insights into the quality of concrete bored foundations immediately after casting, facilitating cost-effective and prompt remediation when warranted.

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